

Zeolite Synthesis: A Comparative Analysis of Conventional Hydrothermal and Microwave-Assisted Methods

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Abstract: ZSM-5 zeolite was synthesized using both conventional hydrothermal and microwave-assisted hydrothermal techniques to investigate the effect of the synthesis approach on its structural and physicochemical characteristics. The precursor gel was subjected either to control aging or to microwave irradiation prior to hydrothermal crystallization at 160 °C under autogeneous pressure. X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns confirmed the successful formation of highly crystalline MFI-type ZSM-5 in both cases, with comparatively higher peak intensity observed for the microwave-treated sample, indicating improved crystallinity. FTIR spectroscopy revealed characteristic framework vibrations, including bands associated with double five-membered ring (D5R) units, confirming the development of the ZSM-5 structure. Thermo gravimetric and differential thermal (TG–DTA) analyses showed sequential removal of adsorbed water and organic template species, demonstrating good thermal stability of the synthesized materials. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images displayed well-defined crystalline morphology, with the microwave-assisted method yielding relatively uniform and elongated nanocrystals as a result of rapid and homogeneous nucleation.

Keywords: Zeolite, microwave, hydrothermal XRD, SEM

Introduction: Zeolites are three-dimensional crystalline aluminosilicate materials that occur both naturally and as laboratory-synthesized compounds. Owing to their well-defined microporous framework, high surface area, and tuneable physicochemical properties, zeolites have found extensive applications in environmental remediation, heterogeneous catalysis, biotechnology, gas sensing, and medicinal fields [1].

Microwave-assisted synthesis has gained considerable attention as an effective approach for zeolite preparation due to its rapid, homogeneous, and volumetric heating characteristics. In contrast to conventional heating methods, which rely on heat transfer through conduction and convection from the reactor walls, microwave irradiation directly interacts with polar molecules and ionic species in the reaction medium, thereby enhancing nucleation rates and

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accelerating crystal growth [2-3]. As a result, this technique significantly reduces synthesis time and overall energy consumption while frequently producing zeolites with high crystallinity, narrow particle size distribution, and well-defined morphology.

Moreover, microwave-assisted hydrothermal synthesis provides improved control over reaction conditions, rendering it a promising and sustainable route for the large-scale synthesis of zeolites intended for catalytic, adsorption, and separation applications. In the present study, a comparative analysis of zeolite synthesis using conventional hydrothermal and microwave-assisted hydrothermal methods is carried out to evaluate the effects of the synthesis route on the resulting material properties.

Materials methods: In the synthesis of ZSM-5 zeolite, four precursor solutions designated as A, B, C, and D were prepared separately. Solution A was prepared by dissolving 1 g of aluminium sulfate in 50 mL of double-distilled water taken in a 100 mL beaker. Subsequently, 16 g of tetraethyl ammonium bromide (TEA-Br) was added drop wise to the solution under continuous stirring using a magnetic stirrer for 15 minutes to ensure complete dissolution and homogenization. Solution B was prepared by adding 96 g of sodium silicate solution (composition: 27.2 wt% SiO₂, 8.4 wt% Na₂O, and 64.4 wt% H₂O) to 45 mL of distilled water, followed by thorough mixing to obtain a uniform solution. Solution C was prepared by dissolving 6.6 g of Sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄) in 50 mL of distilled water in a 100 mL glass beaker. Perchloric acid was used as Solution D without further modification.

Solution A was then added drop wise to Solution B under continuous stirring to form a homogeneous precursor mixture. The pH of the resulting gel was carefully adjusted to 10.3 by the controlled addition of Solutions C and D. The reaction mixture was subsequently stirred vigorously for 1 hour to ensure uniform gel formation. The final oxide molar composition of the synthesis gel was: 78 Na₂O : Al₂O₃ : 270 SiO₂ : 6.9 (TEA)₂O : 7550 H₂O.

The prepared reaction mixture was divided into two equal portions for comparative study. The first portion was allowed to undergo aging at ambient conditions for 17 hours prior to hydrothermal treatment. The second portion was subjected to microwave irradiation at 500 W and 2.45 GHz for 3 minutes in a microwave oven. Following microwave treatment, the resulting hydrogel was immediately transferred to a stainless-steel autoclave without any aging step.

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The microwave-treated gel was heated at 160 °C for 16 hours under autogeneous pressure. After completion of the hydrothermal treatment, the autoclave was allowed to cool naturally to room temperature. The solid product was recovered by filtration and thoroughly washed three to four times with distilled water until the washings were free from residual gel particles. The filtered sample was then dried and subsequently calcined at 500 °C for 4 hours in air to remove and decompose the organic template species.

The aged hydrogel (first portion) was transferred separately into a stainless-steel autoclave and subjected to hydrothermal crystallization at 160 °C for 36 hours under autogeneous pressure. The crystallization time was calculated after the reaction mixture reached the desired temperature of 160 °C. Post-autoclave treatment, including cooling, filtration, washing, drying, and calcination, was carried out following the same procedure as described above.

Characterization: The X-ray diffraction (XRD) pattern of the synthesized ZSM-5 zeolite was recorded over a 2θ range of 5°–60° using Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$). The diffraction pattern exhibits well-defined and intense peaks characteristic of the MFI-type crystalline framework, confirming the successful formation of ZSM-5 zeolite [4].

Fig.1 XRD of ZSM5 zeolite without microwave treatment

The prominent diffraction peaks observed at 2θ values of approximately 23.1°, 23.9°, and 24.4° correspond well with the standard diffraction pattern of ZSM-5 zeolite. The strong and sharp reflections in the 22–25° region, which are typical fingerprint peaks of ZSM-5, confirm the presence of a well-ordered zeolitic structure.

Fig. 2 XRD of ZSM5 zeolite with microwave treatment

The most intense and well-resolved peaks appear in the 2θ range of $22\text{--}25^\circ$, with prominent reflections at approximately 23.1° , 23.9° , and 24.4° . These peaks are considered the fingerprint peaks of ZSM-5 zeolite and match well with the standard diffraction data, confirming the successful formation of the ZSM-5 phase. Furthermore, the relatively narrow peak widths imply well-developed crystallite domains. The enhanced peak intensity, particularly in the $22\text{--}25^\circ$ region, suggests effective nucleation and crystal growth during synthesis. Such features are often associated with optimized hydrothermal conditions and are further enhanced in microwave-assisted synthesis due to rapid and uniform volumetric heating [5].

Fig.3 (a) IR spectrogram of ZSM5 without microwave and (b) with microwave

Figure 3(a) presents the FTIR spectrum of ZSM-5 synthesized via the conventional hydrothermal method. The characteristic structure-insensitive asymmetric stretching vibration of the Si–O–Si framework is observed at 1087.5 cm^{-1} , while the corresponding symmetric stretching vibration appears at 795.9 cm^{-1} . A structure-sensitive asymmetric stretching band,

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indicative of the MFI framework, is detected at 1220.8 cm^{-1} . The presence of a band near 550 cm^{-1} confirms the formation of the double five-membered ring (D5R) structural units, which are characteristic of the ZSM-5 framework. Additionally, a broad absorption band at 3465.8 cm^{-1} is attributed to the O–H stretching vibrations of adsorbed water molecules. Figure 3(b) shows the FTIR spectrum of ZSM-5 synthesized using microwave-assisted treatment [6-7]. The structure-insensitive asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations are observed at 1105.6 cm^{-1} and 798.4 cm^{-1} , respectively. The structure-sensitive asymmetric stretching band appears at 1227.3 cm^{-1} , confirming the development of the MFI-type framework. The band corresponding to the double five-membered ring structure is observed at 545.2 cm^{-1} , further validating the formation of ZSM-5. A broad band at 3436.6 cm^{-1} is assigned to the O–H stretching vibrations of water molecules present in the zeolite structure. The slight shifts in band positions between the conventionally synthesized and microwave-treated samples may be attributed to differences in crystallinity, framework ordering, or local structural environment induced by the synthesis method.

A fig 4 is TG-DTA analysis of ZSM5 zeolite. The weight loss is present in three steps for ZSM5 zeolite. In first step the weight loss is 4.4% (0.302mg) in the temperature range 300K to 408K [8]. It is due to water desorption from zeolite cavities. In the second step the weight loss is maximum and it is 18.87% (1.283mg) is due decomposition of templating species [9]. It is in the temperature

Fig. 4 TG-DTA of ZSM5 zeolite without microwave

range 408K to 468K. In third step the water loss is 2.7% (0.18mg) in the temperature range 468K to 718K. It is attributed to the removal of occluded organics. [10] There is no observable weight

loss above 718K. Two exotherm and one endotherm are observed in DTA analysis of ZSM5. The first exotherm is observed at 363.4K corresponds to oxidative decomposition of residual organic compounds. The second exotherm is found at 483.3K is due to combustion of adsorbed species and the endotherm is found to be present at 426.4K, indicates water loss [11].

Fig.5 TG-DTA of ZSM5 with microwave

The TG-DTA analysis for ZSM5 zeolite with microwave treatment is shown in fig.5. In first step the weight loss is 4.7 % (0.3mg) in the temperature range 300K to 390K due to the water loss. In second step the weight loss is 12.7% (0.82mg) in the temperature range 510K to 750K due to water loss in pores. In the temperature range 750K to 823K the weight loss is found to be 2.51% (0.16mg) in third step due the oxidative decomposition of organic templates. Above 823K no weight loss is observed. The total weight loss is about 19.1% due to dehydration of water present in zeolite cavities and decomposition of templates (TEA-Br). In differential thermal analysis, the exotherm observed at 455.6K is believed due to decomposition of physically occluded TEA-Br template in the zeolite. The exotherm at 549.9K corresponds to decomposition of TEA cations, which are occluded in the zeolite framework [9-10]. The endotherm is observed at 820.9K due to some phase change occurred. The surface morphology of the synthesized ZSM-5 zeolite was examined using scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The SEM micrograph reveals the presence of well-defined, highly crystalline particles with predominantly coffin-shaped and prismatic morphologies, which are characteristic of ZSM-5 zeolite without microwave treatment possessing an MFI-type framework.

Fig. 6 SEM of ZSM5 zeolite (a) without microwave (b) with microwave treatment

The particles appear relatively uniform in shape and size, with crystal dimensions in the sub-micron to micron range, indicating controlled crystal growth during the synthesis process. The well-faceted crystal edges and smooth surfaces suggest a high degree of crystallinity, which is consistent with the sharp diffraction peaks observed in the XRD analysis.

The crystals exhibit a relatively uniform size distribution, with individual particles predominantly in the nanometre range, as indicated by the 500 nm scale bar is shown in fig.6 (b). The elongated morphology suggests preferential crystal growth along specific crystallographic directions, which is typical for ZSM-5 and is often associated with well-ordered channel systems [12]. In microwave-assisted hydrothermal synthesis, this type of uniform and elongated morphology is often attributed to rapid and homogeneous nucleation induced by volumetric microwave heating, leading to enhanced crystallization kinetics compared to conventional hydrothermal methods.

Conclusion: In the present study, ZSM-5 zeolite was successfully synthesized using both conventional hydrothermal and microwave-assisted hydrothermal methods, and a detailed comparative analysis was carried out to evaluate the effect of microwave treatment on crystallization behaviour, structural properties, thermal stability, and morphology.

X-ray diffraction analysis confirmed the formation of a highly crystalline ZSM-5 zeolite with an MFI-type framework in both synthesis routes. However, the microwave-assisted sample exhibited sharper and more intense diffraction peaks, particularly in the characteristic $22\text{--}25^\circ$ (2θ) region, indicating enhanced crystallinity and improved crystal growth kinetics due to rapid and uniform volumetric heating.

FT-IR spectroscopy further supported the successful formation of the ZSM-5 framework, as evidenced by the presence of characteristic bands corresponding to asymmetric and symmetric T–O–T (T = Si, Al) vibrations and the diagnostic double five-membered ring vibration near 550 cm^{-1} . Minor shifts in band positions and improved definition of framework vibrations in the microwave-treated sample suggest better structural ordering compared to the conventionally synthesized zeolite.

Thermo gravimetric and differential thermal analyses revealed multi-step weight loss behaviour associated with desorption of physically adsorbed water, decomposition of organic templates (TEA-Br), and removal of occluded species. The microwave-assisted ZSM-5 zeolite showed a more controlled and reduced template decomposition behaviour, indicating efficient incorporation and removal of the organic structure-directing agent. The absence of significant weight loss at higher temperatures confirms the good thermal stability of the synthesized materials.

SEM analysis demonstrated clear differences in morphology between the two synthesis methods. The conventionally synthesized ZSM-5 exhibited well-defined coffin-shaped and prismatic crystals in the sub-micron to micron range, while the microwave-assisted ZSM-5 showed smaller, elongated, and more uniformly distributed nanocrystals. This morphological refinement is attributed to rapid nucleation and accelerated crystallization under microwave irradiation. Overall, the results clearly demonstrate that microwave-assisted hydrothermal synthesis significantly enhances crystallinity, reduces crystallization time, improves morphological uniformity, and lowers energy consumption compared to the conventional hydrothermal method.

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